

Original article

Almespar: An Open Reading Frames Detection Tool Using Python

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ABSTRACT

Background and aims. Open reading frames (ORFs) are sections of a reading frame that do not include any stop codons. A reading frame is a sequence of nucleotide triplets read as codons indicating amino acids; a single strand of DNA has three potential reading frames. Long ORFs in a DNA sequence may represent possible protein-coding areas. In addition to extended ORFs, which assist in gene locus prediction, there is yet another type of ORFs known as small open reading frames (smORFs), which have 100 codons or fewer. **Methods.** We develop an offline, cross-platform, and dependable detection tool for regular ORFs and smORFs prevalent in biomedical studies. **Results.** In this work, the most ORFs were found in the *Bos taurus* (Cattle) Insulin gene, which had 17 consecutive ORFs, while the fewest ORFs were reported in the *Canis lupus* (Dog) Insulin gene, which had only 4 ORFs. **Conclusion.** The software meets the expected demarcation restrictions. We strongly advise more research into the detection of nested ORFs.

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INTRODUCTION

Molecular biology introduces the open reading frames (ORFs) as stretches of DNA sequence between the start and stops codons [1]. Rapid and accurate identification of all conceivable ORFs from DNA Sequence with known genetic coding appears to be an unpretentious procedure [2,3]. In practice, this process is hampered by DNA sequencing mistakes, which may result in the omission or incorrect assignment of start/stop codons, resulting in longer or truncated ORFs [4–6]. When confronted with a list of all potential ORFs in a genome, determining which ones comprise genes can be challenging [7].

To begin, substantially or completely overlapping ORFs frequently coexist on the same DNA strand [8]. Second, conflicting ORFs are frequently found on distinct DNA strands [9]. Finally, even if no conflicts exist, there is no guarantee that an ORF, specifically a short one, genuinely translates for a protein [10,11]. Numerous genes have been identified that express transcripts with mRNA-like properties, such as capping and polyadenylation, although they do not appear to be translated into proteins; such transcripts are referred to as long non-coding RNAs (lncRNAs) [12–14]. Those genes and their byproducts have fundamentally altered our knowledge of transcriptional regulation [15,16]. An additional form of gene elements complicates our understanding of the genome's coding potential: Small ORFs (smORFs; occasionally known as sORFs) with 10 to 100 codons that are thought to be functional [17–19].

There are huge numbers of small sequences in nucleotide sequences, and several of them may be linked to transcripts, and in many cases, to presumed lncRNAs [20]. As a result, useable smORFs are frequently not annotated because they have still not been empirically verified, and they have not been confirmed because they are not annotated, a challenge that is seldom (and only by chance) surmounted [21]. The issue with algorithmic annotation is that, like canonical

protein-coding ORFs, it is based completely on sequence similarities, which disclose the conservation of the presumed coding sequence, denoting a selective result and thus function; and resemblance to proteins and protein domains with an observationally substantiated function, indicating a comparable performance for the smORF [22,23].

Genes are commonly detected based on the statistically considerable resemblance between translated ORFs and recognized gene products [24–26]. Gene identification approaches based on coding potential evaluation and detection of regulatory DNA elements must be used in the absence of authentic datasets. Identifying ORFs is critical in biochemical and molecular practice. Despite the abundance of ORF detection tools available, most of them were web-based and demanded an internet connection. As a result, the primary goal of this study is to provide an offline, cross-platform, and reliable ORFs detection tool for regular implementation in biological research.

Material and Methods

Data mining

The datasets used to assess the application's efficiency as well as the formulation of probabilistic scenarios, were collected from online, publicly available databases, namely the GenBank databases from The National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI; <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>), on January 18, 2021. Five distinct whole genome shotgun sequences of the INS (Insulin) gene were utilized to characterize various Mammalian species, (a) *Bos taurus*; cattle (accession ID: NC_037356.1), (b) *Canis lupus*; dog (accession ID: NC_051822.1), (c) *Felis catus*; domestic cat (accession ID: NC_058377.1), (d) *Homo sapiens*; human (accession ID: NC_000011.10), (e) *Sus scrofa*; pig (accession ID: NC_010444.4).

The genetic codes matrix

The codons database was obtained from the NCBI taxonomy database, on March 23, 2021, to build the search patterns matrix. NCBI takes considerable effort to guarantee that every coding sequence (CDS) in GenBank data has the correct translation [27]. The meticulous validation of each record's taxonomy and assignment of the right genetic code for each organism and record is key to this endeavor (Table 1).

Table 1. Genetic code in the taxonomy tree

Genetic Code in Taxonomy Tree	Initiation Codons	Stop codons
The Standard Code	TTG, CTG, ATG	TAA, TAG, TGA
The Vertebrate Mitochondrial Code	ATT, ATC, ATA, ATG, GTG	TAA, TAG, AGA, AGG
The Yeast Mitochondrial Code	ATA, ATG	TAA, TAG
The Mold, Protozoan, and Coelenterate Mitochondrial Code	TTA, TTG, CTG, ATT, ATC, ATA, ATG, GTG	TAA, TAG
The Invertebrate Mitochondrial Code	TTG, ATT, ATC, ATA, ATG, GTG	TAA, TAG
The Ciliate, Dasycladacean and Hexamita Nuclear Code	ATG	TGA
The Echinoderm and Flatworm Mitochondrial Code	ATG, GTG	TAA, TAG
The Euplotid Nuclear Code	ATG	TAA, TAG
The Bacterial, Archaeal and Plant Plastid Code	TTG, CTG, ATT, ATC, ATA, ATG, GTG	TAA, TAG, TGA
The Alternative Yeast Nuclear Code	CTG, ATG	TAA, TAG, TGA
The Ascidian Mitochondrial Code	TTG, ATA, ATG, GTG	TAA, TAA, TAG
The Alternative Flatworm Mitochondrial Code	ATG	TAG
Chlorophycean Mitochondrial Code	ATG	TAA, TAG
Trematode Mitochondrial Code	ATG, GTG	TAA, TAG
Scenedesmus obliquus Mitochondrial Code	ATG	TCA, TAA, TGA
Thraustochytrium Mitochondrial Code	ATT, ATG, GTG	TTA, TAA, TAG, TGA
Rhabdopleuridae Mitochondrial Code	TTG, CTG, ATG, GTG	TAA, TAG
Candidate Division SR1 and Gracilibacteria Code	TTG, ATG, GTG	TAA, TAG
Pachysolen tannophilus Nuclear Code	CTG, ATG	TAA, TAG, TGA
Karyorelict Nuclear Code	ATG	TGA
Condyllostoma Nuclear Code	ATG	TAA, TAG, TGA

Mesodinium Nuclear Code	ATG	TGA
Peritrich Nuclear Code	ATG	TGA
Blastocrithidia Nuclear Code	ATG	TAA, TAG, TGA
Cephalodiscidae Mitochondrial UAA-Tyr Code	ATG	TAA, TAG, TGA

Implementation

The benchmarks were all completed using an Intel (R) Core (TM) i5-3470 CPU running at 3.20GHz and 16 GB of DDR3 RAM. Ubuntu Linux Desktop 20.04 LTS/ 64-bit was utilized as the operating system for the benchmarks. Python programming language version 3.9.5 was used to develop the application.

Design

To determine the initialization and stop codons, a modified form of a brute-force algorithm for exact string matching was recruited, the new search begins from the last successful stop codon, so that the ORFs overlapping in this approach cannot be detected, which is considered as one of the methodology's shortcomings (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Almespar ORF finder flowchart

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This project aims to build Almespar, a cross-platform offline software for locating open reading frames (ORFs) over different species. The insulin (INS) gene was utilized as a target in this study to assess the program's reliability in identifying open reading frames in five mammal species. The rediscovery of insulin signifies a genuine milestone,

highlighted by contrasts, arguments, and disagreements among experts, and perhaps even significant frustrations, setbacks, and occasionally optimism [28]. The advent of insulin was a watershed moment in diabetes diagnosis and treatment, radically revolutionizing both therapy and prognosis [29,30]. Diabetes is one of the most researched disorders in medical history, with the oldest mentions dating back to a collection of Egyptian medical scripts written near 1552 BC, known as the Ebers Papyrus [28,31].

Insulin is a crucial hormonal modulator of development and metabolism in mammals and may have a comparable role in many other eukaryotes, while clear structural evidence of insulin-like molecules found outside of vertebrates is still absent [32]. In the lack of insulin, many cells in the body fail to use glucose and amino acids correctly, resulting in severe metabolic derangements [33,34]. In man, the inability to metabolize glucose results in diabetes mellitus, which is characterized by glucosuria, ketonuria, growth arrest, and negative nitrogen balance, eventually leading to death from either acute metabolic acidosis caused by unrestrained fatty acid oxidation or, in the absence of sufficient lipid stores to generate ketone bodies, from inanition - hence the classic description of the body "melting down into urine" in diabetes [35–37]. The terminology open reading frame (ORF) is fundamental in gene discovery. Interestingly, two concepts are being used [38–40]. An ORF is described in all definitions as a span of nucleotide sequence that is not disrupted by stop codons in a specific reading frame, although they diverge in the following: (a) an ORF is a sequence with a distance that is divided by three-letters which starts with a translation start codon (ATG) and terminates with a stop codon as illustrated in figure 2-a, (b) an ORF is a sequence with a length that is divisible by three-letters and is delimited by stop codons as shown in figure 2-b [41–45].

Figure 2. The Two Definitions Leads to Different Open Reading Frames (ORFs)

ORFs in *Bos taurus* (cattle) *INS* gene

The *Bos taurus* *INS* gene (GeneID:280829) spans 1620 pb on Chromosome 29 (Figure 3). The number of ORFs mined was 17 spreads across the gene (Figure 4). The total number of forward ORFs observed was 7, ranging from 60 pb to 786 bp in length. While the lengths of the ORFs detected on the reverse strand were 39 bp to 333 bp (Table 2).

Figure 3. The *Bos taurus* *INS* gene

Figure 4. The *Bos taurus* INS gene ORF distribution

Table 2: *Bos taurus* (Cattle) Insulin gene ORF's

Label	Strand	Frame	Start	Stop	Length (bp)
ORF0	-	1	1200	1125	75
ORF9	-	1	873	559	315
ORF10	-	1	486	436	51
ORF11	-	1	384	271	114
ORF12	-	2	1295	1173	123
ORF13	-	2	788	750	39
ORF14	-	2	527	471	57
ORF15	-	2	116	9	108
ORF16	-	3	1519	1187	333
ORF17	-	3	271	116	156

ORFs in *Canis lupus* (Dog) INS gene

The dog, *Canis lupus* INS gene (Figure 5), Reveals a limited handful of ORFs in both strands (Figure 6). Only two ORFs were detected on the forward strand ranging in length from 264 bp to 333 bp, and two ORFs for the reverse strand were 111 and 342 bp long, respectively (Table 3).

Figure 5. The *canis lupus* ins gene

Figure 6. The Canis lupus ins gene orf distribution

Table 3. Canis lupus (Dog) Insulin gene ORF's

Label	Strand	Frame	Start	Stop	Length (bp)
ORF1	+	2	455	787	333
ORF2	+	3	183	446	264
ORF3	-	2	184	74	111
ORF4	-	3	750	489	342

ORFs in Felis catus (Cat) INS gene

The Felis catus (Cat) INS gene (GeneID:493804) contains only 6 ORFs (Figure 7) dispersed on both strands (Figure 8).

Figure 3: The Felis catus (Cat) INS

Figure 6. The Felis Catus (Cat) Ins Gene Orf Distribution

The total number of forward ORFs found was two, with lengths ranging from 111 pb to 264 bp. The lengths of the ORFs discovered on the reverse strand were 4 ranging from 39 to 531 bp (Table 4).

Table 4: Felis catus (Cat) Insulin gene ORF's

Label	Strand	Frame	Start	Stop	Length (bp)
ORF1	+	1	271	534	264
ORF2	+	1	838	948	111
ORF3	-	1	877	347	531
ORF4	-	2	828	478	351
ORF5	-	2	177	112	66
ORF6	-	3	272	234	39

The Homo sapiens (human) INS gene

The Homo sapiens (human) INS gene (GeneID:3630), Its cytogenetic position Ch38.p13, and composed of 1431 DNA bp (Figure 9). It's comprised of 14 ORFs, disseminate on both strands (Figure 10). The total ORFs number on the forward strand was 5, ranging from 69 bp to 408 bp, while the reverse strand shows 9 ORFs ranging from 33 bp to 297 bp (Table 5).

Figure 9. The Homo sapiens (human) INS gene

Figure 10. The Homo Sapiens (Human) Ins Gene Orf Distribution

Table 5: Homo sapiens (Human) Insulin gene ORF's

Label	Strand	Frame	Start	Stop	Length (bp)
ORF1	+	1	496	903	408
ORF2	+	1	1812	1143	132
ORF3	+	2	239	553	315
ORF4	+	2	911	979	69
ORF5	+	2	1387	1429	123
ORF6	-	1	729	577	153
ORF7	-	2	1013	963	51
ORF8	-	2	827	726	102
ORF9	-	2	656	606	51
ORF10	-	2	497	201	297
ORF11	-	2	35	3	33
ORF12	-	3	1321	1106	216
ORF13	-	3	442	359	84
ORF14	-	3	148	65	84

ORFs in Sus scrofa (pig) INS gene

The Sus scrofa (pig) INS gene (GeneID:397415), is located on chromosome 2 and composed of 1211 DNA bp (Figure 11). It's comprised of 11 ORFs, distributed on both strands (Figure 12). The total ORFs number on the forward strand was 6, ranging from 72 bp to 330 bp, while the reverse strand shows 5 ORFs ranging from 39 bp to 315 bp (Table 6).

Figure 11. The *Sus Scrofa* (Pig) *Ins* Gene

Figure 12: The *Sus Scrofa* (Pig) *Ins* Gene Orf Distribution

Table 6: The *Sus scrofa* (pig) *Insulin* gene ORF's

Label	Strand	Frame	Start	Stop	Length (bp)
ORF1	+	1	70	360	291
ORF2	+	1	874	993	120
ORF3	+	2	98	187	90
ORF4	+	3	30	101	72
ORF5	+	3	432	662	231
ORF6	+	3	831	1160	330
ORF7	-	1	1112	798	315
ORF8	-	2	862	659	204
ORF9	-	2	433	395	39
ORF10	-	2	313	182	132
ORF11	-	3	882	790	93

CONCLUSIONS

In this study, the highest ORFs were reported in the *Bos taurus* (Cattle) *Insulin* gene which scored 17 successive ORFs whereas the lowest score was reported in *Canis lupus* (Dog) *Insulin* gene which shows only 4 ORFs. Generally, the program fulfills the boundary limits as expected. We strongly recommend further work and consider the detection of nested ORFs.

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